

Synthesis and characterization of some heterobimetallic complexes of Cu, Zn and Mn derived from succinoyldihydrazones[†]

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Abstract : Heterobimetallic Cu, Zn and Mn complexes $[\text{ZnCu}(\text{L}^n)(\text{CH}_3\text{OH})_3] \cdot x\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$ (H_4L^1) (1), H_4L^2 (2); $x = 0, 1$), and $[\text{MnCu}(\text{L}^n)(\text{CH}_3\text{OH})_3] \cdot x\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$ (H_4L^1 (3), H_4L^2 (4), $x = 0, 1$) ($\text{H}_4\text{L}^1 = \text{disalicylaldehydesuccinoyldihydrazone}$, $\text{H}_4\text{L}^2 = \text{bis}(2\text{-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde)succinoyldihydrazone}$) have been synthesized using monometallic copper complexes as metalloligand in methanol medium. Complexes have been characterized by means of elemental analysis, molar conductance, UV-Vis, IR spectroscopy, magnetic moment and ESR. The μ_{eff} value for the $\text{Zn}^{\text{II}}\text{-Cu}^{\text{II}}$ complexes fall in the range 1.73–1.75 B.M. while for $\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}\text{-Cu}^{\text{II}}$ complexes fall in the region 3.24–3.43 B.M. Electronic spectroscopy suggests that the copper centre has a pseudo square pyramidal stereochemistry in all the complexes while the second metal centre has a distorted octahedral stereochemistry. The dihydrazones are present in enol form in the complexes. The electron transfer reactions of the complexes have been investigated by cyclic voltammetry.

Keywords : Heterobimetallic, copper, manganese, zinc, spectroscopic techniques, cyclic voltammetry.

Introduction

In recent years, much attention has been devoted to the study of heteronuclear metal-containing compounds^{1–3}. The excitement regarding the study of heterobimetallic complexes is of great interest in the fields of materials science and homogeneous catalysis mainly due to their unusual physical properties and reactivity which homometallic complexes cannot have^{4–7}. In other words, compounds containing two different metal centers exhibit synergistic reactivity that is different from that observed for compounds containing only one type of metal¹. Nature has used combinations of different metal ions in the active sites of many metalloenzymes to catalyze some of the fundamental reactions of biology. This information has motivated chemists to develop protocols for the synthesis of oxo-bridged heterobimetallic compounds with

the prospect of their use as catalysts for many chemical reactions of industrial importance, electronic, magnetic and redox properties⁸. Copper and manganese heterobimetallic complexes also serve as a catalyst for multi electron reduction of O_2 or N_2 ⁹.

A survey of literature revealed that although the metal complexes of monometallic and homobimetallic complexes of dihydrazones were studied in details¹⁰, yet their heterobimetallic complexes have received only little attention in recent years^{11–14}. Moreover, there is not even a single report on existence of heterobimetallic complexes of dihydrazones containing succinoyl fraction. In view of the above importance the present paper reports synthesize and characterization of heterobimetallic complexes derived from some succinoyldihydrazones in which copper is first metal and zinc and manganese are second metal.

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Fig. 1

R ₁	X	Dihydrazone ligand
H	H	Disalicylaldehydesuccinoyldihydrazone (H ₄ L ¹)
5,6-benzo	H	Bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde)succinoyldihydrazone (H ₄ L ²)

Results and discussion

The complexes isolated in the present study have been suggested to have the composition [ZnCu(Lⁿ)(CH₃OH)₃].xCH₃OH (H₄L¹ (1), H₄L² (2); x = 0, 1), and [MnCu(Lⁿ)(CH₃OH)₃].xCH₃OH (H₄L¹ (3), H₄L² (4), x = 0, 1), respectively, on the basis of data obtained from analytical, molecular weight and mass spectral studies. The complexes decompose in the temperature range 289–360 °C. The melting point of the complexes are higher than those of the corresponding parent ligands. This sug-

gests that the metal-ligand bonds in these complexes have more ionic character than those in the corresponding parent ligand. All of the complexes are insoluble in water and common organic solvents but are soluble in highly coordinating solvents such as DMSO and DMF. **2** and **4** show no loss of weight at 80 °C ruling out the possibility of presence of either water molecules or methanol molecules in their lattice structure. On the other hand the remaining complexes showed weight loss at 80 °C equal to one methanol molecule revealing their presence in the lattice structure. Further, the complexes showed loss of weight equal to three methanol molecules at 150 °C. The loss of these methanol molecules at such a high temperature suggests their presence in the first coordination sphere around the metal centre. All of the complexes have been characterized by mass spectrometry. The molecular ions along with their theoretical and experimental masses, for all of the complexes have been given in Table 1. The mass spectra for the complexes **1** and **4** have been shown in Figs. 2, 3. The mass spectral behaviour of the complexes suggests that all of them are dimeric in nature.

Table 1. Peak assignments in the mass spectra and electronic spectral data for the heterobimetallic complexes derived from succinoyldihydrazones

Sr. no.	Complex	Molecular ions	Theo. mass	Expt. mass	Electronic spectral bands λ _{max} (nm), ε _{max} (dm ³ cm ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹) ^a	
					Solid	Solution
1.	[ZnCu(L ¹)(CH ₃ OH) ₃].CH ₃ OH	[Cu ₂ Zn ₂ (L ¹) ₂ (DMSO) ₃] ⁺ [Cu ₂ Zn ₂ L ¹ ₂ (DMSO) ₅] ⁺	1191.84 1347.80	1192.01 1347.84	620	300 (6090), 314 (5098), 384 (5287), 638 (157) [293 (7100), 330 (520)] ^a
2.	[ZnCu(L ²)(CH ₃ OH) ₃]	[Cu ₂ Zn ₂ (L ²) ₂ (H ₂ O)] ⁺	1175.84	1173.64	640	317 (6220), 331 (7154), 403 (7463), 419 (7325), 632 (192) [312 (5400), 327 (6200), 365 (5800), 382 (5400)] ^a
3.	[MnCu(L ¹)(CH ₃ OH) ₃].CH ₃ OH	[Cu ₂ Mn ₂ (L ¹) ₂ (DMSO) ₄ (CH ₃ OH) ₂] ⁺	1313.08	1313.73	400, 600	300 (7333), 317 (6870), 385 (5508), 660 (140) [293 (7100), 330 (5200)] ^a
4.	[MnCu(L ²)(CH ₃ OH) ₃]	[Cu ₂ Mn ₂ (H ₂ L ²)(HL ¹)(DMSO) ₃] ⁺ [Cu ₂ Mn ₂ (H ₂ L ²) ₂ (DMSO) ₄] ⁺	1381.46 1462.46	1381.80 1462.10	400, 615	294 (8934), 331 (9450), 408 (8552), 474 (6030), 630 (170) [312 (5400), 327 (6200), 365 (5800), 382 (5400)] ^a

^aWaves due to uncoordinated ligands.

Fig. 2. Mass spectrum of the complex $[\text{ZnCu}(\text{L}^1)(\text{CH}_3\text{OH})_3]\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$ (1) in DMSO.

Fig. 3. Mass spectrum of the complex $[\text{MnCu}(\text{L}^2)(\text{CH}_3\text{OH})_3]$ (4) in DMSO.

Magnetic moment :

The $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-Zn}^{\text{II}}$ complexes **1-2** have μ_{eff} value per molecular formula in the range 1.73–1.75 B.M. There is an unpaired electron localized on the Cu^{II} centre and the magnetic moment is expected to lie in the range 1.75–1.90 B.M. The μ_{eff} value suggests either no interaction or very weak Cu-Cu interaction in the structural unit of the complexes which may be the result of intermolecular antiferromagnetic interactions between neighbouring dinuclear units.

The $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-Mn}^{\text{II}}$ complexes **3-4** have μ_{eff} value in the range 3.24–3.43 B.M. which is much lower than the theoretical value of $4.923 \mu_{\text{B}}$ ²⁵ expected for two coupled species of $S_{\text{Cu}} = 1/2$ and $S_{\text{Mn}} = 5/2$. This value is very close to the spin-only value of $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 4.923$ B.M. for an $S = 2$ state expected as the ground state of an antiferromagnetically coupled $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-Mn}^{\text{II}}$ complex. This indicates that there is considerably more antiferromagnetic exchange interaction between Cu^{II} and Mn^{II} ions in complex, with resulting $S = 2$ ground state.

Electron paramagnetic resonance :

The X-band EPR spectra for the heterobimetallic complexes have been recorded at RT and LNT in powder as well as DMSO glass at LNT. The various EPR parameters for the complexes have been set out in Table 2. The EPR spectra for **1-4** have been given in Figs. 4-7.

Electronic spectroscopy :

The uncoordinated ligands show two to four bands in the region 285–382 nm (Table 1). The bands in the region 285–327 nm may be attributed to intra ligand $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions while the band in the region 330–382 nm to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition, respectively¹⁵. The band in the region 330–382 nm is characteristic of salicylaldimine/naphthaldimine/*o*-hydroxyacetophenimine part of the ligand¹⁵.

In the solid state, the complexes show broad band centred around 400 nm. This band appears to arise due to overlapping of several bands arising from intraligand band in the region 330–382 and ligand-to-metal charge transfer band severely encompassed by vibrational and rotational transitions.

The Cu-Zn complex **1-2** show non-ligand asymmetric bands in the region 620–650 nm in solid state. Since zinc metal centre is not expected to show any *d-d* transition due to d^{10} configuration, these absorption bands are as-

Table 2. Magnetic parameters for heterobimetallic complexes derived from succinoyldihydrazones

Sr. no.	Complex	Magnetic moment μ_{eff} (BM)	Temp.	Solid/Solution	g_{\parallel} (g_3)	g_{\perp} (g_2)	g_{\perp} (g_1)	$g_{\text{av}}/g_{\text{iso}}$	$A_{\parallel}(A_3)$	$A_{\perp}(A_2)$	A_1	A_{av}	$\Delta M_s = 2$	$g_{\parallel}/A_{\parallel}$	g_3 (M)	g_2 (M)	g_1 (M)	g_{av} (M)		
1.	[ZnCu(L ¹)(CH ₃ OH) ₃] (CH ₃ OH)	1.73	RT	Powder	2.283	-	2.069	2.140	153	-	-	-	-	160.1	-	-	-	-		
			LNT	Powder	2.282	-	2.067	2.139	153	-	-	-	-	-	160.0	-	-	-	-	
			LNT	Solution	2.285	-	2.077	2.146	153	-	-	-	-	-	3.825	147.4	-	-	-	-
2.	[ZnCu(L ²)(CH ₃ OH) ₃]	1.75	RT	Powder	2.281	-	2.077	2.145	150	-	-	-	-	4.195	163.1	-	-	-	-	
			LNT	Powder	2.281	-	2.071	2.141	150	-	-	-	-	-	4.335	163.1	-	-	-	-
			LNT	Solution	2.297	-	2.071	2.146	170	-	-	-	-	-	-	145.0	-	-	-	-
3.	[MnCu(L ¹)(CH ₃ OH) ₃] (CH ₃ OH)	3.43	RT	Powder	-	-	-	2.051	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2.064	
			LNT	Powder	-	-	-	2.051	-	-	-	-	-	-	2.064	-	-	-	-	2.069
			LNT	Solution	2.265	-	2.071	2.136	160	-	-	-	-	-	2.069	-	2.265	-	2.072	-
4.	[MnCu(L ²)(CH ₃ OH) ₃]	3.24	RT	Powder	-	-	-	2.058	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2.070	
			LNT	Powder	-	-	-	2.064	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2.075
			LNT	Solution	2.250	2.077	1.947	2.091	160	20	90	90	-	-	-	-	2.254	-	1.965	-

Fig. 4. EPR spectrum of the complex $[\text{ZnCu}(\text{L}^1)(\text{CH}_3\text{OH})_3]\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$ (1) in DMSO glass at LNT ($f = 9.1$ Mz).

Fig. 5. EPR spectrum of the complex $[\text{ZnCu}(\text{L}^2)(\text{CH}_3\text{OH})_3]$ (2) in DMSO glass at LNT ($f = 9.1$ Mz).

signed to arise due to $d-d$ transition from copper centre only. In view of the asymmetric broad character of the band in the region 500–750 nm and its high intensity at 620, 640, 620 and 670 nm, it is suggested that copper centre in the complexes has distorted square pyramidal stereochemistry in the solid state.

In DMSO solution, complexes show an asymmetric broad band in the region 550–800 nm with maximum

intensity in the region 630–646 nm having molar extinction coefficient in the region $142\text{--}192 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$, respectively, with band position slightly changed. The position of the band together with their molar extinction coefficients suggests that copper centres have distorted square pyramidal stereochemistry (Fig. 10).

Complexes 3-4 also show a broad asymmetric band in the visible region with their centres at 600, 615, 630 nm,

Fig. 6. EPR spectrum of the complex $[\text{MnCu}(\text{L}^1)(\text{CH}_3\text{OH})_3]\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$ (**3**) in DMSO glass at LNT ($f = 9.1$ Mz).

Fig. 7. EPR spectrum of the complex $[\text{MnCu}(\text{L}^2)(\text{CH}_3\text{OH})_3]$ (**4**) in DMSO glass at LNT ($f = 9.1$ Mz).

respectively. The position and the asymmetric nature of the bands reveal square pyramidal stereochemistry for Cu^{II} centre.

In DMSO solution, the $d-d$ band appears at 660, 630 and 643 nm, respectively. Due to extremely weak nature of $d-d$ transition in Mn^{II} centre, these absorption bands are assigned to $d-d$ transition from copper centre only. Further, the molar extinction coefficients of these bands

are 140, 170 and 150 $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$, respectively. The intensity of the band increases as the energy of the absorption band increases suggesting square pyramidal stereochemistry around copper in heterobimetallic complexes **3-4**. The essential features of these bands along with molar extinction coefficient attest the solid state conclusion that the copper centre has five coordinated stereochemistry in DMSO solution¹⁶ as well (Fig. 10).

Fig. 8. Cyclic voltammetry of complex $[\text{MnCu}(\text{L}^1)(\text{CH}_3\text{OH})_3]$ CH_3OH (**3**) at 200 mV/s.

Fig. 9. Cyclic voltammetry of complex $[\text{MnCu}(\text{L}^2)(\text{CH}_3\text{OH})_3]$ (**4**) at 200 mV/s.

Fig. 10. Suggested structure for heterobimetallic complexes $[\text{MCu}(\text{L}^n)(\text{CH}_3\text{OH})_3] \cdot x\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$ (M = Zn, Mn; $\text{H}_4\text{L}^n = \text{H}_4\text{L}^1\text{-H}_4\text{L}^2$; x = 0, 1, 2).

Infrared spectroscopy :

Some structurally significant IR bands for uncoordinated dihydrazones and complexes have been set out in Table 3. All of the complexes show characteristics peaks due to the ligation of the ligands to the metal centre in the KBr-phase IR spectra.

Cyclic voltammetry :

All of the complexes have been characterized by cyclic voltammetry in 2 mM solution at a scan rate of 100 mV/s in DMSO solution because of the solubility reasons in non-coordinating solvents (CH_3CN and CH_2Cl_2) with 0.1 M tetra-*n*-butyl ammonium perchlorate (TBAP) as a supporting electrolyte. The potentials of the complexes were scanned in the potential range +2.0 to -2.0. The cyclic voltammetric data have been set out in Table 4. The cyclic voltammogram for the complexes at a scan rate of 200 mV/s have been given in Figs. 8 and 9.

The complexes **3** and **4** show three reductive waves while **1** and **2** show four reductive waves in the forward scan. On the other hand, **3** shows three oxidative waves while **1** and **4** show four oxidative waves only except **2** which shows five oxidative waves. The complexes show both irreversible as well as reversible redox processes. The reductive waves observed in the region -1.83 to -1.57 and -1.39 to -1.23 V may be attributed to electron transfer reactions centred on the ligand. All these reductive waves are irreversible. Further, on the anodic side also, there is an oxidative wave in the region +1.17 to +1.31 V in **2** and **4** and another oxidative wave in the region +0.88 to +0.95 V in the remaining complexes which are considered to correspond to electron transfer reactions centred on the ligand, most probably, due to oxidation of first and second $>\text{C}=\text{N}$ - linkages, respectively. The remaining redox couples may be attributed to electron transfer reaction centred on the metal ion. **1** to **4** show a reductive wave in the region -0.25 to -0.39 V while the corresponding oxidative wave is in the region -0.10 to -0.24 V. The difference between these reductive and oxidative waves falls in the region 60-200 mV revealing that the redox reaction is either reversible or quasi-reversible. Another reductive wave is observed in the region -0.76 to -1.00 V in the complexes. The corresponding oxidative wave is observed at -0.78, -0.87 and -0.79 V in **1** and **2**, respectively, while the remaining

Table 3. Structurally significant infrared (IR) bands (in cm^{-1}) for succinoyldihydrazones and their heterometallic complexes

Sr. no.	Ligand/Complex	$\nu(\text{OH} + \text{NH})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$	Amide II + $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ phenyl/naphthyl	$\nu(\text{NCO}^-)$	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{N}-\text{N})$ (Phenolate)	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ (Enolate)	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$
	H_4L^1	3446(m) 3235(m)	1675(s) 1639(s)	1604(s) 1623(s)	1530(s)	-	1280(s)	1031(w)	-	-	-
	H_4L^2	3496(s) 3184(s)	1679(s)	1627(s)	1534(w)	-	1249(s)	1073(w)	-	-	-
1.	$[\text{ZnCu}(\text{L}^1)(\text{CH}_3\text{OH})_3]$ (CH_3OH)	3373(s)	-	1604(s) 1619(s)	1533(s)	1509(s)	1300(m)	1036(w)	538(w)	458(m)	852(w) 376(m)
2.	$[\text{ZnCu}(\text{L}^2)(\text{CH}_3\text{OH})_3]$	3384(s)	-	1619(s)	1538(s)	1519(s)	1299(m)	1025(w)	540(w)	466(m)	857(w) 379(w)
3.	$[\text{MnCu}(\text{L}^1)(\text{CH}_3\text{OH})_3]$ (CH_3OH)	3432(s)	-	1598(s)	1574(s)	1531(s)	1303(s)	1019(m)	512(w)	491(w)	374(m)
4.	$[\text{MnCu}(\text{L}^2)(\text{CH}_3\text{OH})_3]$	3448(s)	-	1617(s)	1533(s)	1508(s)	1300(s)	1037(m)	536(m)	463(w)	381(w)

complexes show no such oxidative wave in the anodic scan. The ΔE value for this redox couple is 60 mV in **1** and **2** revealing that the redox reaction is reversible. When the cyclic voltammogram for the complexes are recorded at a scan rate of 200 mV/s, **3** show the corresponding oxidative wave at -0.90 V, giving a difference of 70 mV. This evidences that the second redox couple in **3** is also quasi-reversible. In the remaining complexes, the oxidative wave corresponding to second reductive wave is not observed either at 150 mV/s or at 200 mV/s. This reveals that the species produced corresponding to the second reductive wave is not stable in DMSO solution and reverts back to the original species. Further, large peak separation, most probably, originates from a slow heterogeneous electron exchange rate rather than from intervening homogeneous reaction¹⁷. On the basis of results and discussion given above, the following redox reactions may be postulated for **1** to **3**.

On the otherhand, for **4**, there is only one redox reaction as given below

Conclusion

In all the heterobimetallic complexes, the heterometal centres are tethered to one another through naphthoxide/phenoxide bridging. Copper centre has a pseudo square pyramidal stereochemistry in all the complexes while the second metal centre has a distorted octahedral stereochemistry. The complexes show considerable antiferromagnetic interaction between hetero metal centres. Based on the above physico-chemical and spectroscopic studies the tentative structure of the complexes are proposed.

Experimental

Materials :

Copper acetate monohydrate, zinc acetate monohydrate, manganese acetate tetrahydrate, diethyl succinate, hydrazine hydrate, substituted salicylaldehydes and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde were E. Merck, Qualigens, Hi-Media or equivalent grade reagents. The precursor com-

Table 4. Electrochemical parameters for the heterobimetallic complexes derived from succinoyldihydrazone (potential vs Ag/AgCl) at a scan rate of 100 mV/s

Sr. no.	Compd.	Reduction	Oxidation		ΔE
		E_c	E_a	$E_{1/2}$	
1.	[ZnCu(L ¹)(CH ₃ OH) ₃](CH ₃ OH)	-1.57	-	-	-
		-1.23	-	-	-
		-0.84	-0.78	-0.81	60
		-0.28	-0.14	-0.21	140
		-	+0.11	-	-
		-	+0.94	-	-
2.	[ZnCu(L ²)(CH ₃ OH) ₃]	[-0.84]	[+0.24] ^a		
		-1.47	-		
		-1.39	-		
		-0.93	-0.87	-0.90	60
		-0.26	-0.20	-0.23	60
		-	+0.18		
3.	[MnCu(L ¹)(CH ₃ OH) ₃](CH ₃ OH)	-	+0.88		
		-	+1.17	-	-
		[-0.62]	[-0.68, -1.12] ^a		
		-1.37	-	-	-
		-0.93	-	-	-
		-0.27	-0.14	-0.21	120
4.	[MnCu(L ²)(CH ₃ OH) ₃]	-	+0.99	-	-
		-			
		[-0.58] ^a	[-0.52] ^a		
		-1.29	-	-	-
		-0.92	-	-	-
		-0.28	-0.10	-0.19	180
		-	+0.26	-	-
		-	+0.93	-	-
		-	+1.31	-	-
		[-0.84] ^a	[+0.24] ^a	-	-

^aWaves due to uncoordinated ligands.

plexes [Cu(H₂Lⁿ)(H₂O)] and [Zn(H₂Lⁿ)(H₂O)₂] were synthesized by literature method¹⁸.

Instrumentation and measurement :

Copper, zinc and manganese were determined by standard literature procedures¹⁹. C, H, N was determined by micro analytical methods using Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS/O Analyser II. The molar conductance of the complexes (10⁻³ mol L⁻¹ in DMSO) were measured by a Systronics Direct Reading Conductivity Meter-303 with dip-type conductivity cell at room temperature. Room temperature magnetic susceptibility measurements were made on a Sherwood Magnetic Susceptibility Balance MSB-Auto. Diamagnetic corrections were carried out using Pascals

constant¹⁹. Electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded in DMSO solution on a Perkin-Elmer Lambda-25 spectrophotometer. Electron paramagnetic resonance spectra of the complexes were recorded at X-band frequency on a Varian E-112 E-Line Century Service EPR spectrometer using TCNE ($g = 2.0027$) as an internal field marker. Variable temperature experiments were carried out with a Varian Variable Temperature accessory. Infrared spectra were recorded on a BX-III/FT-IR Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer in the range 4000–400 cm⁻¹ in KBr discs. Far-IR spectra were recorded in the range 600–50 cm⁻¹ in CsI discs. Mass losses were determined by heating the complexes at 110 °C and 180 °C for 4 h in an

electronic oven. Cyclic voltammetric measurements of the compounds in DMSO were done using a CH Instruments Electrochemical analyzer under dinitrogen. The three electrode cell is equipped with a Pt disk working electrode, a Pt wire auxiliary electrode and Ag/AgCl reference electrode separated from the sample solution by a salt bridge; 0.1 mol L⁻¹, TBAP was used as the supporting electrolyte.

Synthesis of [ZnCu(Lⁿ)(CH₃OH)₃].xCH₃OH (H₄L¹) (1), H₄L² (2); x = 0, 1), and [MnCu(Lⁿ)(CH₃OH)₃].xCH₃OH (H₄L¹ (3), H₄L² (4), x = 0, 1) :

The heterobimetallic complexes **1-4** were prepared by using the monometallic copper(II) complexes [Cu(H₂Lⁿ)(H₂O)] (H₄Lⁿ = H₄L¹-H₄L³) as precursors. In order to prepare the complex **1**, the precursor complex [Cu(H₂L¹)(H₂O)] (1.50 g, 2.92 mmol) was suspended in hot methanol (50 mL) with continuous stirring for a period of 15–20 min. This homogeneous suspension was added to zinc(II) acetate solution (3.21 mmol) in methanol (50 mL) maintaining [Cu(H₂L¹)(H₂O)] : metal acetate molar ratio at 1 : 1.1. The resulting reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 h. The precipitate thus obtained was filtered and washed with hot methanol, 20 mL each time and finally with diethyl ether (30 mL) and dried at 70 °C.

The remaining complexes **2**, **3** and **4** were also prepared essentially by the above method adding precursor copper(II) complexes to the zinc(II) acetate (**2**) and manganese(II) acetate solution (**3**, **4**), respectively in methanol. Yield : 60–80%.

[ZnCu(L¹)(CH₃OH)₃].xCH₃OH (**1**) : Yield : 2.60 g (78%), m.p. : 342 °C; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₂H₃₀N₄O₈CuZn (%) : Cu, 10.97; Zn, 10.77; C, 43.50; H, 4.92; N, 9.23. Found : Cu, 10.67; Zn, 10.45; C, 43.80; H, 4.89; N, 9.24; Mol. wt. (theo. : (606.94), exp. : (791 ± 40); Molar conductance (DMSO, Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) : 1.5.

[ZnCu(L²)(CH₃OH)₃].xCH₃OH (**2**) : Yield : 2.23 g (72%), m.p. : > 360 °C. Anal. Calcd. for C₂₉H₃₀N₄O₇CuZn (%) : Cu, 9.42; Zn, 9.69; C, 51.56; H, 4.44; N, 8.29. Found : Cu, 9.81; Zn, 9.39; C, 51.36; H, 4.41; N, 8.69; Mol. wt. (theo. : (674.49), exp. : (813 ± 41); Molar conductance (DMSO, Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) : 1.6.

[MnCu(L¹)(CH₃OH)₃].xCH₃OH (**3**) : Yield : 2.45 g (85%), m.p. : 358 °C; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₂H₃₀N₄O₈CuMn

(%) : Cu, 10.93; Mn, 9.19; C, 44.12; H, 5.01; N, 9.36. Found : Cu, 11.23; Mn, 8.89; C, 43.92; H, 4.99; N, 9.56; Mol. wt. (theo. : (598.39), exp. : (780.55 ± 40); Molar conductance (DMSO, Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) : 1.7.

[MnCu(L²)(CH₃OH)₃].xCH₃OH (**4**) : Yield : 2.45 g (85%), m.p. : > 356 °C; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₉H₃₀N₄O₇CuMn (%) : Cu, 9.56; Mn, 8.28; C, 52.37; H, 4.51; N, 8.43. Found : Cu, 9.86; Mn, 8.78; C, 51.87; H, 4.48; N, 8.83; Mol. wt. (theo. : (664.55), exp. : (803 ± 40); Molar conductance (DMSO, Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) : 1.8.

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